

EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF BUSINESS ACTIVITY IS AN IMPORTANT CONDITION FOR ENSURING ECONOMIC SECURITY

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Abstract. *This article describes the role of economic security in the country's development, the methods used to ensure it, its interrelationship with the country's security, entrepreneurial activity and its effective management, and its contribution to the development of the financial market. The main task of entrepreneurs is to protect the economic interests of the state and ensure its economic security. Ensuring economic security not only in foreign, but also in domestic economic activity includes issues such as combating violations of customs regulations, preventing illegal currency transactions, filling the state budget through timely and correct collection of customs and tax payments. In this article, some directions of effective management of business activities and provision of economic security in external and internal economic activities are considered.*

Keywords: *entrepreneurship, economic security, foreign and domestic economic activity, customs fees, currency transactions, shadow economy, digital economy, tax payments.*

INTRODUCTION

Ensuring the country's economic security is a guarantee of its independence and stability. Economic security is one of the important conditions of state security. It establishes state control over national resources, regulates foreign economic activity from the point of view of protection of national interests, increases the country's economy and production power.

At first glance, the concept of "economic security" means that economic interests are free from danger, protected. When talking about the importance of the state management body in ensuring economic security, it is not necessarily from the point of view of protecting the interests of a person or group, but its importance in the security of the national economy, which embodies the interests of the individual, group, society and the state, is explained. In this sense, the concept of "economic security" is new in the terminology of Uzbekistan's economy management bodies. In the practice of the management structures of foreign countries, it is a concept that has been used for a long time and is widely interpreted.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

According to the interpretation of Russian economist V. Pankov, "National economic security is such a state of the economy that it is characterized by its "sustainable immunity" to the influence of external and internal factors that allow the continued continuation of socio-economic processes, which derails the achieved standard of living of the population and creates strong social tension in the society, as well as threats to the sovereignty of the state".

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

The role of business activity and its effective management is important in ensuring the country's economic security. To control this, we need tax and customs authorities and their services. The Law "On State Customs Service" stipulates that customs authorities shall perform tasks such as protecting the economic interests of the Republic of Uzbekistan and ensuring its economic security, carrying out customs control and clearance of goods entering the territory of the country, collecting customs fees within the scope of their powers.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Today, our economy is developing more and more. Our main goals are to develop the country in all aspects, to ensure its stable economic and social development, to take a place among the developed countries, and to enter the ranks of the world financial markets. Taking this into account, a number of reforms, new projects and programs are being developed and put into practice.

The concept of "economic security" is one of the new areas in the Uzbek economy. It ensures the security of the country's economic resources. As the economic potential of the country develops, the number of imported goods entering the country from abroad also increases. In this regard, it is important for the country to know whether each incoming product is legally brought into the country and to what extent it affects the health of the population. This, in turn, creates the need for economic security in the country. In fact, economic security is also a part of the country's security in some sense. In the conditions of economic reforms aimed at the transition to market relations, the state should ensure the economic security of the activities of economic entities and prevent harm to citizens. For these purposes, the state should, first of all, develop measures to improve the business environment, increase the share of small and medium-sized businesses in the country's economy, develop the competitiveness of economic sectors, and form the stock market, land and real estate markets. Protection of economic interests is carried out on the basis of the policy of the state strategy and the concept of economic security. It aims to protect the economic interests and national wealth of the Republic of Uzbekistan from internal and external threats. This concept is the main document defining the policy in this regard.

By developing economic security, we will be able to further improve the financial market. Let us take a look at the banking system, which is of special importance in the development of the financial market. For the stable operation of banks, the trust of the society in the entire banking system should be high. Then the idle funds of the population, the accumulated funds are kept by the bank. As a result, money circulation in banks is accelerated and their stable condition is maintained. If we look at the banking system of foreign developed countries, in particular, the Swiss banking system, which is considered the most famous in the world. One of the unique aspects of this bank is that it is not related to the current taxation system, that is, the income from banking operations reaches the depositors in a pure form, without charging any additional fees. In addition, deposit boxes have a highly coded system, and information confirming the identity of the deposit holder is also kept secret. The rights of bank users are highly protected, and this, in turn, strengthens their trust in the bank. In our country, the safety of deposits is somewhat underdeveloped. A person who puts money in a deposit does not expect to receive it tomorrow without any losses. Therefore, the level of savings in the hands of the population shows a slightly higher indicator. Further improvement of the banking system, increasing the trust of society,

ensuring the safety of their money and valuables stored in various deposit boxes will serve to strengthen financial stability.

Economic security, in turn, is ensured using certain methods. The method of factor analysis is used to find and collect information about the security of the person, society and the state. Economic risk cannot be studied without factor analysis, because economic security is also a system, which is associated with a number of variable events. The study of economic security factors is related to the indicators (indicators) known as the factor matrix. The factor matrix characterizes the degree of interdependence of the factors and indicators determined during the analysis. The main purpose of the factor analysis is to develop general rules that ensure the economic security of the individual, society and the state and to ensure their integral connection with the shortcomings in the process of development of the economy and social sphere of our country. In general, it is not for nothing that economic security is emphasized as the security of the country. It is very important that every product consumed by the population is ready for the level of consumption. The stronger the country's economic security is developed, the more consumable and high-quality the incoming goods and manufactured products are, the safety of society is ensured, and they are protected from diseases that may occur due to various unsuitable products.

DISCUSSION

Therefore, in the development of the country, it is important to be able to ensure its economic security. This, on the one hand, is considered to be national security, and on the other hand, it serves as the basis of economic development.

Researches conducted by well-known scientists show that the work of an entrepreneur in his field of activity is multifaceted. It is determined by the change of market policy or the influence of internal and external factors of the enterprise. However, the main goal of an entrepreneur is to make a profit, as well as to carry out activities that ensure efficient operation in the market. To do this, it is necessary to create a mechanism based on modern management methods that support entrepreneurship and ensure its effective use. When managing a business in market conditions, it is necessary to take into account its following features:

- ensuring economic security is an important condition for effective management of business activities;
- an entrepreneur always works taking into account the demand and supply in the market;
- the entrepreneur makes efforts to ensure efficiency and looks for ways to reduce production costs;
- persons who are responsible for the final results of the business, create sufficient opportunities to conduct their small business under free conditions;
- the final results of a small enterprise, i.e. its profit or loss, will be known only in the process of trading in the market;
- an entrepreneur engaged in small business does not know for sure what risks he will face in the market or what the final result will be.

As the country's economy grows, external conditions and internal factors change, and under its influence, the country's economic interests are formed anew. Therefore, on the one hand, the concept of economic security requires constant change and clarification, on the other hand, it can be observed that the country's economic security, interests, and risks are defined according to the practice of a certain historical period or country.

Now, the goods imported by the entrepreneur are cleared through an automated program and released in a short time without human intervention. Later, the "Customs Audit" program selects and inspects the risk object through analytical methods.

CONCLUSION

It is clear to all of us that the fierce economic competition in the world and information attacks are becoming more and more intense. Unfortunately, instead of diminishing, such hotbeds of turbulent tension are increasing. Taking into account such a dangerous situation, we must strengthen our activities to strengthen peace and tranquility in our country, to fight against various threats. This is the need of the hour. In order to ensure economic security, it strives to create conditions of mutual harmony between the national economy and the world community, which do not hinder the processes of reproduction and provide an opportunity to sharply reduce the risk of threats. In order to ensure the economic security of the country, it is necessary to end dependence on imports of basic products and to strengthen the export of finished products. For this purpose, it is necessary to radically change the structural structure of the country's economy, to transform the economy focused on the production of raw materials and intermediate products into a product focused on export. Only then, the economic situation of the country will not depend on changes in the world markets and resource prices.

To ensure the economic security of the country, it is appropriate to implement the following:

- bringing the strategy of social institutions closer to each other, implementing institutional changes that allow to coordinate their activities;*
- control over compliance with laws and regulations by economic entities and government bodies;*
- ensuring cooperation between government bodies, including the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the Ministry of Internal Affairs, Customs and others, NGOs in the fight against corruption and ensuring economic security;*
- creation of a mechanism for resolving disputes and conflicts arising in the field of economic relations;*
- organization of personnel training in modern methods of analysis of economic activity of enterprises and evaluation of investment projects;*
- increase economic stability in the society and prevent the growth of social tensions;*
- comprehensive development of economic and political relations with near and far foreign countries, taking into account the country's economic interests.*

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated June 5, 2020 No. PQ-6005 "On reforming the customs administration and improving the activities of the state customs service bodies of the Republic of Uzbekistan".
2. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 24, 2018 No. PF-5582 of November 24, 2018 "On additional measures to increase the efficiency of the State Customs Service of the Republic of Uzbekistan."
3. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Foreign Economic Activity". T., 2000.
4. Sh. R. Qobilov. Iqtisodiy xavfsizlikni mustahkamlashning ilmiy nazariy asoslarini takomillashtirish. Monografiya. Toshkent – 2017.

5. Tulkunovna, U. D., & Miromilovich, M. S. CHALLENGES OF CHEMISTRY AS A MEANS OF DEVELOPING EDUCATION.
6. Yunusova Ozoda Anvarjon qizi, Y. O. A. qizi. (2019). MAMLAKAT IQTISODIY XAVFSIZLIGINI TA'MINLASH, UNING HAR TOMONLAMA RIVOJLANISHI GAROVIDIR. Мамлакат иқтисодий хавфсизлигини таъминлашнинг устувор йўналишлари, 1(1), 3. Извлечено от https://tsue.scienceweb.uz/index.php/iqtisodiy_xavfsizlik/article/view/27
7. Батиров, Ф. А. (2023). ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБРАЗОВАНИЕ В СИСТЕМЕ ДОПОЛНИТЕЛЬНОГО ОБРАЗОВАНИЯ. Conferencea, 30-33.
8. Усмонова Дильноза Тулкуновна. (2023). ТЕХНОЛОГИЯ ПОЛУЧЕНИЕ ЦЕЛЛЮЛОЗЫ ИЗ ДРЕВЕСИНЫ. Conferencea, 116–121. Retrieved from <https://conferencea.org/index.php/conferences/article/view/2561>
9. Усмонова Дильноза Тулкуновна. (2023). ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ И ЗАКОНОМЕРНОСТИ ИХ ДЕЙСТВИЯ. Conferencea, 70–73. Retrieved from <https://conferencea.org/index.php/conferences/article/view/2533>
10. Усмонова, Д. Т. (2023). ЭКОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ФАКТОРЫ И ХИМИЧЕСКИЕ ПРОЦЕССЫ ОКРУЖАЮЩЕЙ СРЕДЫ. Conferencea, 183-187.
11. Усмонова, Д. Т. РАЗВИТИЕ ЗНАНИЙ УЧАЩИХСЯ ПРИ ОБУЧЕНИИ ХИМИИ В ШКОЛЕ. ТОШКЕНТ-2021, 32.